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Implementation of Tourism Development Policy in Geopark Ciletuh-Pelabuhanratu, West Java, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

The Ciletuh-Pelabuhanratu National Park area has been designated as a geopark area since 2015 by the Central Government and three years later, in 2018, it was designated as a Global Geopark Network by UNESCO. Since being designated as a geopark area, this area has been increasing a lot, especially in the tourism sector with the recorded number of tourists being 14,723,559 visitors in 2019-2020. The purpose of this report is to analyze the various regulations used in the management and development of the UNESCO Global Geopark area and their application through a study of the Attractions, Accessibility, and Amenities (3A) components of tourism. The results of this study state that the implementation of the policy for the development of tourism areas in Ciletuh Bay has not run optimally, marked by difficult accessibility also inadequate facilities and infrastructure. So, it requires cooperation from various parties, including the government, the private sector, and the surrounding community in the form of active participation and investment.

Keywords: Accessibility, Amenities, Attractions, Tourism, Ciletuh-Pelabuhanratu National Park, Geopark, West Java

INTRODUCTION

Tourism is a system that involves travel and temporary stay by a person outside the area of his residence for one or several days with the aim of getting amusement (Leiper, 1979). Tourism activities have become one of the centres of industrial activity since the global tourism boom in the 1960s-1980s, mostly in developing countries which made coastal tourism a key tourist attraction (Dodds, 2007). According to the World Tourism Organization (2009) in Chang (2011), international tourist arrivals continued to increase from 438 million in 1990 and reached 922 million in 2008 with an average annual increase of 3.8% from 2000 until 2008. Tourism development has several goals with the main objective focused to reduce poverty where the development of tourism activities is expected to be able to contribute for the economic development in the destination area, and its impact will affect the community around the area from global tourism as well as support the realization of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) of the United Nations (Saarinen & Rogerson, 2014).

As mentioned in Dahles (1998), the development of the tourism industry since the 1980s also boosts the economy outside the oil sector. Indonesia is one of the countries with the highest tourism development in Southeast Asia, contributing to 13% in 2008 (Chang, Khamkaew, Tansuchat, & McAleer, 2011). In the early stages of its development, the lower levels economy had not benefited from government measures and regulations to facilitate growth in the tourism sector in Indonesia, so this development led to unrest and increased competition between small traders which irritated tourists and made competitors more competitive that resulted in reduced income. Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 10 of 2009 states that the objectives of tourism activities in Indonesia include: (a) increasing economic growth, (b) improving people's welfare, (c) eradicating poverty, (d) overcoming unemployment, (e) conserving nature, the environment, and natural resources, (f) advancing culture, (g) elevating the nation's figure, (h) fostering a sense of love for the homeland, (i) strengthening national identity and unity, and (j)

strengthening international unity. Indonesia is the largest archipelagic country which makes it has many areas that can be used as tourism destinations, including Bali Province (Sutawa, 2012), West Nusa Tenggara Province (Kurniawan, Adrianto, Bengen, & Prasetyo, 2016), West Java Province (Wilkinson & Pratiwi, 1995; Achmad Rizal, 2021), and many more.

The Regional Development Planning Agency (RPPD) of Sukabumi Regency in 2005-2025 stated that the priority of tourism development is directed for the creation of the Sukabumi tourist destination as one of the leading tourism destinations in West Java, where competition in the tourism sector is getting sharper, requiring each region to continue exploring the potential of its natural resources to be able to sell, attract, and be visited by tourists. One form of tourism development in Sukabumi Regency is the inauguration of the Ciletuh Geopark as a National Geopark in 2015 and then as UNESCO Global Geopark Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu in 2018. Geopark is an area that has geological heritage sites with characteristics and beauty that need to be protected. The area must pay attention to the protection, development of education, science, culture, and socio-economic values (Patzak & Eder, 1998). The development of tourism activities in West Java prioritizes its values of diversity, uniqueness, and cultural and natural wisdom as well as human needs for tourism, mainly in Sukabumi Regency.

Geopark UNESCO Global Geopark (UGG) Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu administratively covers the northern part of Ciemas District to the southern part of Ciracas District, Sukabumi Regency. UGG Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu has a unique characteristic with a semicircular landscape overlooking the Indian Ocean with a diameter of +15 km (Imran & Soedarsono, 2019). In addition, the wealth of natural resources in the UGG Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu area, such as the diversity of ecosystems, biota, and the diversity of the surrounding culture is one of the main attractions there. In addition, regulations are the basis for the management and development of a geopark, because its management does not only require tourist destinations, but also requires feasibility and development on aspects of facilities and infrastructure that have sustainable values so that they can be enjoyed by future generations to come.

Based on the explanation above, there are several objectives of this report, which is discussing the various regulations used in the management and development of the UNESCO Global Geopark area and their application through studies on the components of attractions, accessibility, and amenities (3A) of tourism [1-34].

DESCRIPTION OF THE UNESCO GLOBAL GEOPARK CILETUH-PALABUHANRATU AREA

Geopark Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu area is administratively located in Sukabumi Regency, West Java Province, Indonesia. The name Ciletuh comes from the Sundanese language which consists of three words, which are "Ci" which means "water", "Leuteuk" which means mud, and "Kiruh" which means cloudy. So it can be interpreted as muddy water or river. The area has a total area of 1260 km² consisting of the City of Palabuhanratu and seven sub-districts covering the Districts of Cisolok, Cikakak, Simpenan, Waluran, Ciemas, Ciracap, and Surade, and 74 villages (**Figure 1**). The idea of a concept area with geological, biological, and cultural diversity with the principles of conservation, education, and sustainable development made this area included in the UNESCO Global Geopark in 2018 (UNESCO, 2018).

Geomorphology of the Ciletuh Geopark area is surrounded by stretches of alluvial sediment with varied topographic characteristics and complex rocks. This area is a collision

between two plates, the Indo-Australian Plate (Ocean) which is composed of basalt and the Eurasian Plate (continental plate) which consists of granite to produce pelagic sedimentary rocks, metamorphic rocks, and igneous rocks. In addition, the rock exposed in the Ciletuh area is in the form of a horseshoe that opens to the Indian Ocean (Rahmawati, 2021). The unique potential of the geological aspect in the Ciletuh area can be developed into a competitive tourism destination, in addition to the geological aspect of the Ciletuh Geopark area, which has biodiversity and culture while maintaining local wisdom.

The development of the UGG Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu area aims to provide protection for its geological diversity, biodiversity, cultural diversity, as well as improve the economy of the surrounding community. This development also provides opportunities for the development of local communities, by reducing the unemployment rate, as well as providing opportunities for the creation of new products, new jobs, and new recreational activities for local communities.

TOURIST ATTRACTIONS IN THE UNESCO GLOBAL GEOPARK CILETUH-PALABUHANRATU AREA

With an area that covers many spaces, the UGG Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu area has various attractions for tourists, ranging from natural beauty such as conservation areas on land and coast, waterfalls, social environment, and local culture. In addition, this area also has a cultivation area which includes ponds, farms, conservation areas, and agro-tourism tourism areas, which are coastal, marine, waterfall (Santoso et al., 2018).

Currently, geotourism is one of the breakthroughs that make it easier for tourism activists to increase knowledge about natural resources, cultural identity in tourist areas, and how to preserve them (Farsani et al., 2011).

A) Natural Resources Attractions

The following are various natural resource attractions in the UGG Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu area (**Figure 5 to Figure 82**):

1. Cikepuh Wildlife Sanctuary Area
2. Cibanteng Nature Reserve
3. Turtle conservation area, Pangumbahan
4. Conservation Forest Cipeucang
5. Beautiful landscapes
6. Rare rock types and fossils
7. Unique rocks
8. Small islands
9. Caves
10. Waterfalls
11. Various types of beaches

B) Socio-cultural

Attractions Resource attractions in the UGG Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu area (**Figures 88 to 100**)

1. Cultural Village (Adat Kasepuhan)

2. Archaeological sites
3. Historic buildings
4. Arts
5. Traditions
6. Legends/Myths
7. Batik Villages
8. Turtle hatchlings released by tourists

Various kinds of tourism potential owned is an added value to be an advantage and even a prerequisite for an area to be declared a geopark area that has diversity other than geological diversity.

ACCESSIBILITY IN THE UNESCO GLOBAL GEOPARK CILETUH-PALABUHANRATU AREA

Accessibility is the ease of reaching tourist destinations including comfort, safety, and travel time. It is important because the higher the ease of access, the easier it is to achieve the comfort value for tourists to visit. Transportation activity is one of the initial prerequisites for tourism activities because it links the tourists to their destinations (Toth & David, 2010). The transportation subsystem in tourism activities includes the number of vehicles originating from tourist routes as well as services that facilitate travel such as capacity, travel speed, a form of infrastructure (alternative roads, public transportation, etc.).

Roads to the Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu Geopark Area can be accessed through two routes, the first one is Kiara Dua Line and the second is Cikidang/Cibadak Line. Before the opening of a new route (Cikidang), access to the Geopark Area was only available via the Kiara Dua route; this route was a detour through Kiara Dua, Simpang Waluran, Malereng, Taman Jaya, to Palangpang Beach. The path can be said to be poor and longer as seen from the damaged roads, lack of street lighting facilities, and prone to landslides. Another route that can be taken to reach the Geopark area is through Cikidang. On this route, tourists will be spoiled with beautiful views of the hills and expanses of the sea along the way from the Bagbagan area to Palangpang Beach. This new line can cut travel time up to about 1.5 hours. However, there are still shortcomings in this route, including winding paths and steep ups and downs, and inadequate facilities such as street lighting, rest areas, and re-fueling places (**Figure 2** to **Figure 4**).

AMENITIES IN THE UNESCO GLOBAL GEOPARK CILETUH-PALABUHANRATU AREA

An increase in community activities in tourism areas has also increased the need of comfort for tourists. The convenience of visitors in tourism areas does not only include the availability of lodging and restaurants but also includes the form of services provided by local area managers for visitors by developing the area through facilities and infrastructure in the area, such as the availability of road signs and trash cans.

Based on the explanation in the attractions and accessibility section, the UGG Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu area has great potential as a tourism area, but the ease of accessibility is still

relatively low. The level of comfort/amenities for tourists in their travel experience is also an equally important factor such as hotels or inns and places to eat (**Figure 83** to **Figure 87**). The development of the number of inns, places to eat, and the number of visitors in Sukabumi Regency are shown in **Table 1** and **Table 2**.

Table 1. Number of hotels development and restaurants in Sukabumi District.

Heritage	2015	2016	2017	2018
Hotel	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
1. Two Stars	1	1	1	1
2. Three Star Hotels	1	1	1	1
3. Four Star Hotels	1	1	1	1
Inns, Lodgings	128	128	140	140
Restaurants				
1. Sunda	63	63	63	63
2. Indonesia	4	4	4	4
3. Others	2	2	2	2

Source: Tourism Office of Sukabumi Regency

Table 2. Number of Tourists Visiting Tourist Attractions in Sukabumi Regency

Year	Tourism Site		TOTAL
	International Tourists	Domestic Tourists	
2015	115,548	3,380,193	3,495,741
2016	115,547	3,485,066	3,600,523
2017	112,810	3,657,767	3,770,577
2018	127,145	3,719,483	3,846,628
2019-2021	481,050	14,242,509	14,723,559

Source: Tourism Office of Sukabumi Regency

Based on the above values, there is no significant increase in both the number of lodging and the number of tourists visiting from 2015 to 2021. However, the number of domestic visitors continues to increase even though it is insignificant, so it is estimated that there are factors that do not support visitor comfort, it could consist of a lack of facilities and infrastructure, it could also be due to lack of promotion and cooperation.

A study conducted in Pahang, Malaysia, regarding Holiday Satisfaction from domestic and international tourists, indicates that tourist satisfaction is highly dependent on services such as lodging, tourist agencies, ticket services, information services for tourists, and easy access to the area. In addition, the availability of experience, especially for cultural performances, is also needed (Sukiman et al., 2013). To meet the needs of tourists in the UGG Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu area, there are minimarkets and businesses run by local communities.

GOVERNMENT REGULATIONS

In the development and management of the Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu UGG area, there are several applicable regulations, both local government regulations and management regulations from UNESCO as the organization that manages the Global Geopark. The regulations include:

- a. Presidential Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia No. 9 of 2019 concerning the Development of Taman Bumi Geopark.

This regulation was made with the aim of being a guideline for the central government, local governments, and stakeholders in developing geoparks. Geopark development is carried out by the central government and local governments involving stakeholders by prioritizing the development of tourism destinations. Based on this regulation, geopark management must pay attention to the protection and preservation, the linkage between geological heritage, geological, biological and cultural diversity as a unified resource. In its development, the geopark area must also provide guidance and supervision through outreach, advocacy, technical guidance, training, promotion, and the strengthening of geopark networks.

- b. West Java Governor Regulation No. 48 of 2006 concerning the Regional Tourism Development Master Plan (RIPPD) of West Java Province.

This regulation contains tourism development policies from various aspects, such as regional aspects, tourism product development, market and marketing development, tourism institutional development, and human resource development.

- c. West Java Governor Regulation No. 72 of 2018 concerning the Development of Geopark Areas in the West Java Province.

This regulation is intended to be a guideline for the Provincial Government in carrying out the development of geopark areas in the province by sustainably maintaining the conservation function, in which it regulates the preparation of geopark development governance, the development of the implementation of the collaboration of stakeholders, developing the role and participation of the community and the business world to improve the welfare of the community and to supervise and control the development of geoparks. The central government and district/city governments can collaborate in the form of infrastructure support, financial assistance, promotion,

regional development, socialization of existence, implementation of promotions, preservation of sustainability, maintenance of peace, order, community economic development, and community empowerment. In implementing this regulation, it is also necessary to involve universities, the business world, construction of infrastructure, providing assistance, increasing economic growth, and facilities for local communities in increasing income.

- d. Regional Regulation of Sukabumi Regency No. 22 of 2012 concerning Regional Spatial Planning for Sukabumi Regency for 2012-2032.

The tourism potential in the UGG Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu area has become a superior product and is stated in Regional Regulation Number 22 of 2012 concerning Regional Spatial Planning (RTRW) of Sukabumi Regency for 2012-2032 which has an explicit goal of realizing an efficient, productive, sustainable and competitive regional spatial planning in the fields of agribusiness, tourism and industry towards a developed and prosperous district. This confirms that tourism development will be the leading sector.

- e. Sukabumi Regent Regulation No. 25 of 2021 concerning the Master Plan of the UNESCO Global Geopark Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu 2020-2029.

This regulation contains plans to realize the development of the UNESCO Global Geopark Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu in a directed, integrated and sustainable manner by combining the values of protection, education, and local economic development.

CONCLUSION

Based on the study of existing regulations relating to the management and development of the Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu UGG Area as well as looking through the tourism components, which are Attractions, Accessibility, and Amenities, it is known that the implementation of policies for developing tourism areas in Ciletuh Bay has not run optimally, marked by poor accessibility as well as incomplete facilities and infrastructure. Therefore, cooperation from various parties, including the government, the private sector, and the surrounding community is needed in the form of active participation and investment.

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APPENDIX

Figure 1. Map of UGG Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu

Figure 2. Scenery around UGG Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu

Figure 3. Scenery around UGG Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu

Figure 4. Scenery around UGG Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu

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Figure 18. Beach

Figure 19. Cikadal Beach

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Figure 69. Cisolok Hot Spring

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